

SPHINX

Site: TEMPLE Season GS 79-80Area: N. COLONNADE Square R16 Locus Number ③

Progress of Excavation 23/1/80 R16A1: After planing its surface,
Removed ③ "clean sand" from R16 N Balk to New N Balk
≈ 60 cm from previous N Balk. ③ Lay against ③b - both slope
against deposit ④-④d. Became clear darker more compact slightly
clay-like sand lower part of ③ as previously designated for R16
actually ③b and R16 N Balk amended. ③b signaled as more
compact (easy to follow its natural contours) w/ patches of darker
more compact - moist (only feature of drying?) slightly clay like sand.
At higher E end and lower W end of ③-③b the two levels →

Locus Description CLEAN SANDLocation in Square Across surface R16A1 sloping up to EUnder Locus ②-②a Over Locus ④ E end; FLOOR on W end
banked against ④-④d (which is out)Locus Dimensions 5-15 cm thick varyingLevels 8.99- 8.24 sloping down to W end less radically to SAnalysis of non-artifactual materials Small chips of granite, dolerite, alabaster.

(Sampled separately from limestone). Fine limestone material (not
 concentrated, 1 larger chunk roundish limestone, 1 small insect body
 remains.

do not have sharp demarcation but "finger" or interface into one another.
Notable that more compact tan clay-like (3b) under rectangular limestone block in E Balk on which in turn rests toppled c.b.

31/II/80 R16A2: Took out (3) quickly with large trowel. Sifted.
Taken back to S.T. N. Wall. Contains fine to middling limestone frags.
Some sherds, including some diagnostic. Few granite and dolerite chips (these saved). 1 large dolerite chip. 2-3 very small corroded iron (ore?) frags w/ stone samples (nat. inclusion?). 2-3 smooth quartz pebbles.
Small flakes dolerite. Very few alabaster.

3 sherds Diagnostic, one: }

NOTE: MOD. FOIL-WRAPPER FROM SIFTING (3).
AND MOD. GLASS FRAG.